

Environment and its influence

Flight duration of the brown planthopper

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Brown planthopper (BPH) annually migrates to the summer rice growing areas of China, Japan, and Korea. These migrations are windborne and move in the same direction and at the same speed as the wind. We used weather maps to determine the duration of flight of BPH caught on ships on the East China Sea in Jun and Jul 1973 and 1981. The BPH data were collected by Japanese scientists Iijima and Oya.

Trajectories were drawn upwind from the ships from the time of insect capture until a potential source of macropterous BPH was reached. BPH have been caught at heights of up to 1.5 km. and as wind speed and direction change with height, trajectories were drawn in the 10-m and 1.5-km wind fields.

During the study, the centers of a series of depressions passed north of Japan from west to east. Strong southwesterly winds at the surface and 1.5 km occurred in the warm sectors of the depressions and were present when BPH were caught (Fig. 1). South of Japan, air flowing toward the depressions was influenced by the clockwise flow out of the North Pacific Subtropical Anticyclone and southerly or southeasterly winds were common over the Ryukyu Islands and occasionally blew in China and parts of Japan (Fig. 2).

The change in wind direction as the depressions passed affected the location of sources. Trajectories at 10 m or 1.5 km or both linked all 33 captured samples to potential sources — usually in mainland or Taiwan, China (Fig. 1), but twice, the 10-m trajectory ended in the Ryukyu Islands (Fig. 2). Simulated flights between those locations and the ships lasted

1. Source area southwest of ship. 1.5 km wind field at 0000 GMT (0800-0900 local time) on 27 Jun 1981.

2. Source area southeast of ship. 10 m wind field at 0000 GMT (0800-0900 local time) on 1 Jul 1973.

between 9 and 30 h. Trajectories were extended beyond the ships and all but two reached South Korea or Japan, 18 in 30 h or less.

These flight duration estimates are similar to those obtained in the laboratory for BPH from the tropics, suggesting that long distance migration also occurs in the tropics.

Full details of this study have been published in *Ecological Entomology* 8(3):341-350 (1983). □

